

Micellar Catalysis – Effect of Sodium Lauryl Sulphate in the Oxidation of Cyclopentanol by Chromic Acid

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Cyclopentanol oxidation by Cr^{VI} in presence and absence of sodium lauryl sulphate (NaLS) is first order in both the reactants. However, the acid dependence changes from a mixed order in absence of NaLS to pure second order in presence of NaLS. The oxidation rate decreases monotonically with [NaLS] above critical micellar concentration. The observation has been rationalised in the light of both Menger-Portnoy model as well as Berezin's model. One of the reactants, viz. Cr^{VI} is partitioned between the micellar and aqueous phase.

Micellar and other organised media have been successfully used to affect the rate of chemical reactions¹. Essentially the reactions in such media are influenced by hydrophobic and electrostatic forces². We have recently examined several reactions³ involving electron transfer processes in micellar media. It has been possible to get some information regarding the nature of forces affecting the reactions. In continuation of our attempts to understand the electron transfer reactions in the micellar media, we report here the oxidation of cyclopentanol by Cr^{VI} in presence of sodium lauryl sulphate (NaLS).

Results and Discussion

Oxidation of cyclopentanol by Cr^{VI} under the condition of cyclopentanol $\gg \text{Cr}^{\text{VI}}$, exhibited the following kinetics. The reaction is first order in Cr^{VI} at constant acidity as seen from the linearity of $\log \text{Cr}^{\text{VI}}$ against time plots. Pseudo-first order rate constants with respect to Cr^{VI} are observed to be constant when the kinetics were carried out in presence of varying $[\text{Cr}^{\text{VI}}]$. Order with respect to cyclopentanol was evaluated from kinetic data obtained under varying cyclopentanol concentration at constant $[\text{Cr}^{\text{VI}}]$ and $[\text{H}^+]$. Plot of the pseudo-first order rate constants (k_{ψ}) obtained in presence of different cyclopentanol concentration against cyclopentanol concentration is straight-line passing through the origin and $k_{\psi}/[\text{substrate}]$ values are constant, demonstrating that the order with respect to cyclopentanol is unity. The data are given in Table 1.

Dependence in $[\text{H}^+]$: The kinetic data in presence of varying acid concentration but constant [oxidant], [substrate] and temperature are presented in the Table 2. Plot of $k_{\psi}/[\text{H}^+]$ against $[\text{H}^+]$ yields a straight-line with a positive slope and positive intercept. The dependence in $[\text{H}^+]$ follows the rate law,

$$\frac{-d[\text{Cr}^{\text{VI}}]}{dt} = a[\text{H}^+] + b[\text{H}^+]^2 \quad (1)$$

TABLE 1—RATES FOR THE OXIDATION OF CYCLOPENTANOL BY Cr^{VI} IN AQUEOUS MEDIUM

[Cyclopentanol] mol dm ⁻³	$\times 10^5 k_{\psi}$ s ⁻¹	$\times 10^3 k_{\psi}/[\text{cyclopentanol}]$ mol ⁻¹ dm ³ s ⁻¹
0.005	5.34 4.16 ^a	10.7 —
0.01	10.92 11.78 ^a	11.0 —
0.02	25.39 22.20 ^a	12.7 —
0.03	40.97 36.16 ^a	13.6 —
0.04	44.12 52.18 ^a	11.0 —
0.05	58.63 54.9 ^a	11.7 —
0.1	121.77 143.1 ^a	12.1 —

^aIn presence of NaLS (8.0×10^{-3} mol dm⁻³).

The Cr^{VI} oxidation of secondary alcohol has already been observed⁴ and is consistent with the formation of chromate ester which is sufficiently basic to take up another proton. Thus breakdown of the ester intermediate as the slow step has been established by earlier worker⁵.

Activation parameters for the oxidation process in aqueous media in different acidities (Table 3) have been computed from $\log k_{\psi}/T$ vs $1/T$ plots at 35–45°. Data indicate that entropy of activation being large negative remains constant when the acidity of the medium is changed. The constancy of $\Delta S^{\ddagger}$ over the hydrogen ion concentration range as well as in NaLS may be a pointer to the operation of identical mechanism in presence of varying $[\text{H}^+]$ and [NaLS]. However, the enthalpy of activation is reduced indicating increase in the equilibrium constant of the process. The observation is in conformity with the accepted view that Cr^{VI} oxidation normally proceeds through the formation of an ester intermediate decomposing in a slow step to yield the products. Hence it may be concluded

TABLE 2-RATE CONSTANTS FOR THE OXIDATION OF CYCLOPENTANOL BY Cr^{VI} IN PRESENCE OF SODIUM LAURYL SULPHATE IN AQUEOUS MEDIUM AT DIFFERENT TEMPERATURES

[Cr^{VI}] = 9.4 × 10⁻⁴ mol dm⁻³, [Cyclopentanol] = 2.0 × 10⁻² mol dm⁻³
 [H⁺] mol dm⁻³ [NaLS] mol dm⁻³ × 10⁵ k_ψ (s⁻¹)

[H ⁺] mol dm ⁻³	[NaLS] mol dm ⁻³	35°	40°	45°
0.25	0.00	4.67	7.24	12.84
	0.001	4.40	6.75	11.47
	0.005	4.20	5.50	9.26
	0.008	4.00	7.32	9.50
	0.01	3.37	6.20	10.40
	0.03	3.21	6.03	9.80
	0.05	2.91	6.10	8.24
	0.07	5.47	6.01	8.45
	0.1	5.21	5.73	7.97
0.38	0.00	13.83	19.46	25.38
	0.001	12.68	14.75	21.90
	0.005	12.36	15.34	23.36
	0.008	12.75	20.02	22.20
	0.01	12.28	17.82	21.81
	0.03	12.91	16.54	21.57
	0.05	10.16	13.20	17.90
	0.07	7.30	11.43	16.20
	0.1	10.02	11.21	16.11
0.475	0.00	-	-	41.11
	0.008	-	-	39.1
0.633	0.00	-	-	59.26
	0.008	-	-	65.2
0.791	0.00	-	-	85.98
	0.008	-	-	111.4
0.950	0.00	-	-	123.1
	0.008	-	-	139.1

that the cyclopentanol too forms a stable ester with Cr^{VI} in a rapid pre-equilibrium step which is evident from the large negative entropy of activation. The mechanism of the process can be illustrated by the following steps :

The breakdown of the chromate ester to products, occurs by cleavage of the C-H bond involving either hydrogen ion⁶ or hydride ion⁷ transfer. This has been well-documented.

TABLE 3-ACTIVATION PARAMETERS IN Cr^{VI} OXIDATION CYCLOPENTANOL IN AQUEOUS MEDIUM

[Cr^{VI}] = 9.4 × 10⁻⁴ mol dm⁻³, [Cyclopentanol] = 2.0 × 10⁻² mol dm⁻³

[H ⁺] mol dm ⁻³	[NaLS] mol dm ⁻³	ΔH [‡] kJ mol ⁻¹	-ΔS [‡] JK ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹
0.25	0	79.4	175
0.38	0	46.4	174
0.25	0.008	73.56	177
0.38	0.008	35.53	176

Oxidation in presence of sodium lauryl sulphate : The kinetic features for the oxidation of cyclopentanol by Cr^{VI} in presence of the anionic micelle sodium lauryl sulphate are as follows.

The dependence in cyclopentanol as well as in Cr^{VI} concentration in presence of constant [H⁺] (0.38 M) and NaLS (0.008 M) is unity as seen from the linear plots of k_ψ versus [cyclopentanol] and constancy of k_ψ values at different Cr^{VI} concentrations (Table 1).

Dependence in [H⁺] : The rate is observed to increase with increase in [H⁺] (Table 2). Plot of k_ψ/[H⁺] against [H⁺] is linear and passes through the origin. The observation indicates the second order dependence of the oxidation rate on [H⁺] in presence of sodium lauryl sulphate. This observation in turn is different from the acid dependence observed in absence of the lauryl sulphate where a mixed dependence i.e. both a first and second order dependence in acid concentration are observed for the rate.

This clear cut difference in the acid-dependence in presence of sodium lauryl sulphate is interesting and needs explanation.

Effects of salt concentration : It is observed that the rate constant k_ψ decreases exponentially with increase in [K₂SO₄] (Table 4). The reason for this observation may be as follows.

TABLE 4-RATE CONSTANTS FOR THE OXIDATION OF CYCLOPENTANOL BY Cr^{VI} IN PRESENCE OF SODIUM LAURYL SULPHATE IN AQUEOUS MEDIUM IN DIFFERENT K₂SO₄ CONCENTRATIONS

[Cr^{VI}] = 9.4 × 10⁻⁴ mol dm⁻³, [Cyclopentanol] = 2.0 × 10⁻² mol dm⁻³, [H⁺] = 0.155 mol dm⁻³, [NaLS] = 1.0 × 10⁻² mol dm⁻³, Temp. = 35°

Sl no.	[K ₂ SO ₄] mol dm ⁻³	10 ⁵ k _ψ s ⁻¹
1.	0	4.19
2.	0.001	2.71
3.	0.005	1.0
4.	0.01	2.1
5.	0.05	1.02
6.	0.1	0.59

Presence of potassium and sulphate ions around the Stern layer may result in the increase of surface potential of the micelle which in turn assist attraction of the active chromium species into the micellar surface excluding the cyclopentanol in the aqueous medium. This will give rise to depletion of the chromium species in the aqueous phase and hence the retardation of the rate with increasing concentration of K₂SO₄. For this reason the reactions were carried out in absence of the added salts.

Effect of sodium lauryl sulphate concentration : Plots of k_ψ against [NaLS] show gradual decrease of rates after a minimum surfactant concentration of 0.01 to 0.02 M. Below this optimum concentration the effect of sodium lauryl sulphate on the rate does not exhibit any definite trend. However, above the optimum concentration (broadly the CMC) of the surfactant the oxidation rate decreases (Fig. 1).

Plot of k_{ψ} vs [NaLS]. 10^4 $[Cr^{VI}] = 9.4 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, [cyclopentanol] = 0.02 mol dm^{-3} , solvent = water : (1) $[H^+] = 0.25 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, temp. = 45° and (2) $[H^+] = 0.38 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, temp. = 40° .

Mechanism : Since the activation entropy and enthalpy in presence of sodium lauryl sulphate (Table 3) are same as those obtained in absence of the surfactant, the mechanism of oxidation of cyclopentanol in presence of NaLS would broadly remain same, i.e. a bimolecular transition state of cyclopentanol and Cr^{VI} would be involved. However, in the pure aqueous medium mixed $[H^+]$ dependence led to postulation of a chromate ester and a protonated chromate ester both decomposing to the products. In presence of NaLS however, second order dependence in acid was only observed and this suggests that a protonated species of chromic acid may be involved rather than chromic acid arising from the following equilibria.

This protonated species of chromic acid, i.e. $H_3CrO_4^+$ is responsible for the oxidation of cyclopentanol in presence of the surfactant through the formation of the protonated ester and subsequent decomposition (eqns. 3 and 5).

In order to account for the observed micellar effect in the oxidation of cyclopentanol by Cr^{VI} , an attempt was made to employ the Menger-Portnoy model⁸ which takes into consideration solubilisation of one reactant only into the micellar phase (Scheme 1)

Scheme 1

The relevant expression is

$$k_{\psi} = \frac{k_w + k_m K_s ([D] - cmc)}{1 + K_s ([D] - cmc)} \quad (7)$$

where, k_{ψ} is the observed pseudo-first order rate constant, $Ox(w)$ the oxidant in aqueous phase, $Ox(m)$ the oxidant in micellar phase, K_s the binding constant of the oxidant, k_w the rate constant in aqueous medium, k_m the rate constant in micellar medium, and $[D]$ the concentration of micelles. Equation(7) can be rearranged to

$$\frac{1}{k_{\psi} - k_w} = \frac{1}{k_w - k_m} + \frac{1}{(k_w - k_m) K_s ([D] - cmc)} \quad (8)$$

When the kinetic data were fitted into equation (8) no linearity was observed implying that the model is inadequate for the present reaction. As the rate was observed to decrease monotonically in presence of the micelle, k_m was neglected in the equilibria which resulted in equation (9).

$$\frac{1}{k_{\psi}} = \frac{1}{k_w} + \frac{K_s ([D] - cmc)}{k_w} \quad (9)$$

To test the validity of the equation $1/k_{\psi}$ was plotted against $([D] - cmc)$ and the plots were observed to be linear. However, the foregoing equations do not enable us to compute the binding constant of the substrate nor give any information regarding partition of the substrate in aqueous and micellar phase. Therefore phase separation approach of Berezin *et al.*⁹ was employed to derive such information.

Berezin *et al.* derived the rate of a bimolecular reaction in presence of dilute surfactant solutions above cmc as given by equation (10),

$$k_{\psi} = \frac{k_m K_A K_B C + k_w}{(1 + K_A [C]) (1 + K_B [C])} \quad (10)$$

where, k_m is the rate constant in micellar medium, k_w the rate constant in aqueous medium, K_A and K_B are the binding constants of the two reactants with the micellar phase and C is the concentration of the surfactant less the critical micellar concentration. In the present study, as the reaction rate was observed to decrease monotonically with [NaLS] above cmc, it may be possible that k_m in equation (10) can be neglected. Thus the equation can be modified to

$$k_{\psi} = \frac{k_w}{(1 + K_A [C]) (1 + K_B [C])} \quad (11)$$

In order to compute the values of K_A and K_B , the graphical method was employed. The equation (11) can be rearranged to the form,

$$\left(\frac{k_w}{k_p} - 1 \right) \frac{1}{[C]} = \alpha + \beta [C] \quad (12)$$

To test the validity of equation (12) the left-hand side term was plotted against $[C]$ which was found to be fairly linear. From the slope and intercept α and β were obtained which could be used to compute K_A and K_B values. Incidentally K_B values are negative implying that one of the reactants, i.e. cyclopentanol is not solubilised and hence not bound to the micellar phase. The magnitude of K_A value (Table 5) is similar to K_S values already evaluated by Menger-Portnoy model modified by Bunton¹⁰. The fair agreement between two sets of values K_A and K_S obtained by using two different models suggests that the oxidation of cyclopentanol by Cr^{VI} in presence of sodium lauryl sulphate can be explained by the reaction scheme (Scheme 1)

lisation. Stock solutions of surfactant ($\sim 0.5 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$) and chromium(VI) oxide ($\sim 0.1 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$) were used. Reactant solutions of cyclopentanol and chromic acid were prepared by dilution of an appropriate amount of the stock solutions. Surfactant was always added to the oxidant flask. Chromic acid was found to be unstable in the presence of the surfactant (NaLS). The decomposition of CrO_3 with different surfactant concentration under a particular set of experimental conditions was computed by plotting k_{dec} against $[NaLS]$ ($dec = \text{decomposition}$). Both the reagents were thermostated for 15 min to attain thermal equilibrium and the reactions were initiated by mixing 25 ml of each at the desired temperature. The progress of the reaction was followed by withdrawing 5 ml aliquots of the reaction mixture at different time intervals and discharging it into excess of KI solution in CO_2 atmosphere. The liberated I_2 was titrated against standard sodium thiosulphate solution using starch as indicator. As the Cr^{VI} concentration in the oxidant flask changed at higher temperature, necessary correction was applied as already mentioned to obtain pseudo-first order rate constants. Results were reproducible within the limits of experimental error.

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TABLE 5. BINDING CONSTANT (K_A) IN THE MICELLAR MEDIUM FOR THE OXIDATION OF Cr^{VI} BY CYCLOPENTANOL IN AQUEOUS MEDIUM

$[Cr^{VI}] = 9.4 \times 10^{-4} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $[Cyclopentanol] = 2.0 \times 10^{-2} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ [H ⁺] mol dm ⁻³	K_A		
	35°	40°	45°
0.028	22.7 (26.5)	-	-
0.25	17.1 (35.9)	3.4 (9.7)	6.9 (17.3)
0.38	3.4 (17.5)	12.3 (12.3)	4.6 (16.4)

Values in parentheses are obtained from Berezin equation and are same as K_A of eqn. (11)

From the average of K_A values using the relationship, $K_A = (P_\gamma - 1) V'$ (where V' is the molar volume of the micellar phase¹¹, $\sim 0.3 \text{ M}^{-1}$), P_γ was derived to be $\sim 65.6 \text{ M}^{-1}$. This is not very large and suggests that the reactant chromic acid is weakly bound to the micellar phase preferably by electrostatic attraction. This is not unreasonable in view of the dependence of the oxidation on the second power of the $[H^+]$ which has led to the postulation of participation of protonated chromic acid species, i.e. $H_3CrO_4^+$ resulting in the equilibrium,

On the other hand as already said cyclopentanol is not micellar bound. Thus the oxidation of cyclopentanol is postulated to be taking place in the aqueous phase and retardation in presence of the micelle is due to the removal of chromic acid species from the aqueous phase into the micellar phase with increasing concentration of NaLS.

Experimental

All the chemicals were of A.R. grade. Cyclopentanol (Koch Light) and chromic acid (E. Merck) were used as such. All solutions were prepared in deionised water. Sodium lauryl sulphate (NaLS) was used after recrystal-